
ATHLETIC PERFORMANCE ENHANCING ACE, ACTN3, AMPD1 GENETIC MARKERS, FITNESS CHARACTERISTICS, C-REACTIVE PROTEIN AND URIC ACID OF CRICKET, NETBALL, RUGBY AND SOCCER PLAYERS: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Sports is a large industry with vibrant leagues running in many countries. Some of the most popular sports are soccer, rugby, cricket and netball. To meet the demand for better performance of athletes and sustain this growing industry, coaches and trainers have depended on the manipulation of factors such as physical and physiological parameters, nutrition, tactics, techniques and psychological factors to try and improve the performance of athletes. These have been referred to as the environmental or nurture constraints. The quest for better performance continues hence microtechnology such as accelerometers, heart rate monitors and global positioning systems are also being used to gather data to determine some of the physical and physiological demands of games. Evidence from studies with twins revealed that there are performance traits which are genetically determined. Research also shows that more than 60% of performance in sport and exercise is genetically determined. The unraveling of the human genome and advances in molecular biological studies resulted in the quest for knowledge relating to the influence of genes at the molecular level on performance in exercise and sport. The human genome project established approximately 20 000 genes in humans. To date, the gene map for performance and health-related fitness phenotypes has identified more than 200 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with some performance and fitness linked traits. Among the most studied gene polymorphisms are the angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) gene, the human α -actinin-3 (ACTN3) gene and the adenosine monophosphate deaminase (AMPD1) gene, as they relate mostly to anaerobic and aerobic related activities. The use of hematological and biochemical indicators to identify injuries and exercise stress calls for exploration of association between gene polymorphisms and indicators such as C-reactive protein, uric acid and blood parameters such as red blood cells and sub-components of leukocytes.

Key words: Biomarkers, genes, polymorphism, sports, performance

INTRODUCTION

Sports have become a large industry with vibrant leagues running in many countries. Although the population of participants is relatively low, female sport leagues are also beginning to be taken as seriously as male leagues.

In South Africa, rugby, soccer cricket and netball are very popular sports. In 2017, it was estimated that there were 9.1 million players among the world rugby union members in 121 countries. Among these, 2.4 million were female players and 603 455 of these were from

South Africa (World Rugby, 2017). South Africa hosted the world rugby cup in 1999 and the Soccer world cup in 2010. (Molly, Chetty, 2015; World Rugby, 2017). The estimated number of people playing the game of soccer world wide as of 2006 was 265 million. (McCabe, Collins, 2018). Netball has an estimated 20 million players in 80 countries and in 2010 South Africa had half a million players in schools and 9 700 adult players (Ferreira, Spammer, 2010; Mclean, 2019).

As a result of the popularity of these sports, training demands are becoming increasingly complex and very scientific, calling for analysis and structures to meet the specific needs of each sport and player. There have been efforts to improve sport performance utilizing scientific principles. Exercise and sporting movement activities are either dynamic or static. Dynamic movements involve change in length of muscles with rhythmic joint movements and the energy metabolic processes in dynamic movements are largely aerobic (Mitchell, Haskell, Snell & Van Camp, 2005). The increasing dynamic component is rated from the estimated percent of maximal oxygen consumption (MaxO_2) achieved during competition, ranging from low to high, where *A.* Low is ($<40\% \text{MaxO}_2$), *B.* Moderate ($40\% -70 \text{MaxO}_2$) and *C.* High ($>70\% \text{MaxO}_2$) (Mitchell et al., 2005). Mitchell et al., also state that there are activities on the other end of the continuum whose muscle energy metabolism is mainly anaerobic, and that they develop force with minimal or no change in muscle length or joint movement. The contraction of muscles on this anerobic side of the spectrum is also referred to as maximal voluntary contraction (MVC) and is also graded from low to high as follows; *I.* low ($<20\% \text{MVC}$), *II.* Moderate ($20-50\% \text{MVC}$) and *III.* High ($>50\% \text{MVC}$) (Mitchell et al. 2005).

Cricket, netball, rugby and soccer can be classified by the above characterization. Soc-

cer is classified as *IC*, which means that it has a low anerobic, low maximal voluntary muscle contraction with a high maximal oxygen consumption and high dynamic component, rugby is *IIB*, Cricket is *IA* and netball is *IIC* (Mitchell et al., 2005). This classification is largely physical and physiological whereas in any exercising scenario the muscles accomplish mechanical (physical) and metabolic (physiological) demands (Houweling et al., 2018). The above classification suggests that cricket is low on both its aerobic and anaerobic demands, netball has moderate anaerobic demand and high aerobic demand. On the other hand, rugby is moderate on both anaerobic and aerobic requirements. However, soccer like netball has a high aerobic component but low anaerobic component.

To satisfy the ever-increasing demand for better performance of athletes and sustain the growing industry of sport, coaches and trainers now depend on the manipulation of the physical and physiological parameters, as shown in the classification above. The physical, physiological, nutrition, tactics, technique and psychological factors are called environmental or nurture constraints (MacArthur, North, 2004; Gibson 2009; Pitsiladis et al., 2016). Family studies in human movement covering identical and dizygotic twins over and above what is mentioned above also show that genetics has a contributing factor to the phenotype of sport performance (Guth, Roth, 2013; Slizik et al., 2017). Evidently, performance in sport and physical activity is a factor of both environmental or nurture constraints and genetic or nature constraints (Puthucheary et al., 2011; Ahmetov & Fedotovska, 2015). The contribution of the genetic or nature factors to athletic status is estimated to be more than 60% while the environmental factors contribute a mere one third (De Moor et al., 2007). As a result, studies have progressed at the molecular lev-

el with the use of genotyping to identify the genes and their variants which contribute to the physical and physiological basis of human performance in sport and exercise. Through genetically profiling athletes, this knowledge would be critical and helpful towards talent identification, strengthening of the training of athletes as well as identifying risks such as susceptibility to injuries (Davids, Baker, 2007; Slizik et al., 2017). The use of genetic information for research in exercise and sport has been further facilitated and enhanced by the completion of the human genome project in 2003 and the advancement of sequencing technologies (Houweling et al., 2018).

The human genome project has shown that there are approximately 20 000 genes in humans. Gene nomenclature has been established for each known human gene in the form of an approved gene name and symbol (short form abbreviation). Each symbol is unique, and each gene is only given one approved gene symbol (Carninci, Hayashizaki, 2007). Using information from the human genome project, scientists in sport science have investigated the association or linkages of genes and performance as well as health related and fitness phenotypes. This resulted in the compilation of the human gene map for performance and health-related fitness phenotypes and 120 DNA polymorphisms related to sports genomics had been identified by December 2014 (Ahmetov, Fedotovskaya, 2015). Polymorphism as a form of gene variation occurs when two or more alleles exist in a population and is related to biodiversity. Alleles are one or two alternatives of the gene that occupy the same locus (place) on a chromosome. The data available for physical performance phenotypes from the genes studied are: cardio respiratory endurance, elite endurance athletes' status, muscle strength, speed and power together with some muscle performance traits including exercise

intolerance of differing degrees (Bray et al., 2009; Ahmetov, Fedotovskaya, 2015). Energy systems, considered in the association studies, fit with the sport classification presented above. Sport teams such as cricket, netball, rugby and soccer variously fit as already illustrated (Mitchell et al., 2005).

Study approaches which are followed with gene markers are mostly case-control studies where mostly elite athletes (case) are compared to the general populations of non-athletic individuals (control) and cross-sectional studies where athletes and the general population are measured quantitatively (Ahmetov, Fedotovskaya, 2015; Houweling et al., 2018). Biomarkers are characteristics that are objectively measured and evaluated as indicators of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or pharmacologic responses to an intervention (IOM (Institute of medicine), 2011). There are several biomarkers which are variously linked to physical performance and gene polymorphisms among which are C-reactive protein and uric acid. Allgrove et al., (2012) observe that exercise of elevated intensity compromises the immune system leaving athletes susceptible to illness. Therefore, hematological parameters such as leucocytes have been used as possible markers of a compromised immune system due to exercise (Mackinnon 1997; Gleeson, Walsh 2012). In this regard, soccer and rugby players have regular aerobic and anaerobic training regimes which expose them to oxidative stress (Yamaner, 2010).

METHOD

Data sources

Four hundred and fifty (450) searches were conducted and the following key words were used: ACE, ACTN3, AMPD1 polymorphisms; athletic performance; exercise, fitness and performance genomics; endurance and resistance training; Uric acid and C-Reactive protein

biomarkers in rugby, soccer and netball. Keyword searches identified articles from Medline (1987-), Research databases: Science direct (2009-), Human Kinetics (2002-), Human Gene Map for Performance and Health-related Fitness Phenotypes, the 2002 Update and the 2006-2007 update and Research Gate (2015-).

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria for this review were a) ACE genotypes and associations with training response, aerobic endurance performance, VO_2 max, long distance athletes, games (rugby, cricket, soccer, netball), high intensity activities of short duration, power output, exercise efficiency, muscle efficiency; b) ACTN3 genotype associations with anaerobic performance; isometric and isokinetic muscle strength, properties of fast twitch and slow twitch muscle fibers in short distance athletes, games, Wingate test and pick power on response to strength training; c) AMPD1 genotypes and associations, anaerobic Wingate test for power, pick power output, mean power, muscle fibers distribution and overall strength; d) Associations of ACE, ACTN3 and AMPD1 genes with physical, physiological characteristics and blood parameters in various sports. The genotype frequencies of the polymorphisms included are presented in accordance with the genomic browsers of the USA, Indian and Arab populations (Bhagi et al., 2002; Al-Hinai et al., 2002; Salem, Batzer 2009).

Exclusion Criteria

Excluded were other potential performance enhancing genes associated with training responses and health-related phenotypes in endurance and power athletes which include, a) ADRB2 (adrenergic receptor beta 2 gene); b) VEGFA (vascular endothelial growth factor gene); c) BDKRB2 (bradykinin beta 2 receptor gene); d) NOS3 (nitric acid synthase 3 gene); e) PRARA (peroxisome proliferator activated

receptor alfa gene) and f) PRARD (peroxisome proliferator receptor delta gene).

DISCUSSION

Performance demands cricket, rugby, netball and soccer

The discussion below further illustrates the performance demands of the four team sports which are both aerobic and anaerobic. This corresponds with the polymorphisms of the genes *ACE*, *ACTN3* and *AMPD1* which encode for either aerobic or anaerobic performance, except for *AMPD1* which only encodes for anaerobic performance.

Cricket

Modern cricketers are now exposed to greater physical and physiological demands. Heart rate can reach 190 beats/min and the predominant contribution from the anaerobic energy systems can contribute up to 60% of the total energy in multiple activities of short duration of less than 40 seconds (Noakes, Durant, 2000). Martens (2004) identified the following demands of cricket: low to moderate aerobic capacity, moderate anaerobic capacity, moderate strength and flexibility, low to moderate endurance and moderate to high speed. Fast bowling has been linked with a mesomorphic somatotype, greater percentage of type II muscle fibers and superior phosphagenic and glycolytic metabolic pathways together with eccentric muscle strength (Stuelcken et al., 2007). A shorter stature and isokinetic knee and shoulder strength were seen to be contributory to the success of batsman (Noakes, Durant, 2000; Nunes, Coetzee, 2007).

Netball

Netball is a fast-paced contact sport (Soh et al., 2007; Chandler et al., 2014). Players must be endowed with speed to run short distances on the court. They perform repeated powerful jumps, well balanced landings, sudden chang-

es of direction and quick stops and starts which require agility (McManus, Stevenson & Finch, 2006; de Villiers, Venter, 2014). Both aerobic and anaerobic energy systems are a requirement (Soh, Husain & Soh, 2006; Soh, Husain & Soh, 2007; Terblanche, Venter, 2009). Using time motion analysis, centers (C) were found to have the highest player load while the goal keepers (GK) and the goal shooters (GS) had the least player loads (Fox et al., 2013; Bailey et al., 2017). The distances covered during matches are estimated to be 4210 meters for GS and 7984 meters for C (Chandler et al., 2014). Injuries occur mostly to ligaments of the ankle, knee, fingers, hands and wrists, (Langeveld, Coetzee & Holtzhausen, 2012; Hervert, Deakin & Sinclair, 2014).

Rugby

Rugby is a high-speed contact sport that involves aerobic and anaerobic fitness, there is a combination of both low and high intensity activities. In elite games running covers 5-8 km with speeds of 18-20 km/h. (Gabbett et al., 2007; Goh et al., 2009). Props are taller, heavier and their skin folds are thicker than other positions, their higher body mass helps them with momentum for their larger tackling role (O'Connor, 1996; Gabbett, 2006). Brower et al., 1994 showed that hookers, centers and wingers have better performance times in the 10 and 40-m speed tests than props who were also slower than the back rowers and outside back positional groups, and backs showed significantly faster times than forwards. The hookers/halves and outside backs had superior $VO_2\text{max}$ than the props positional groups with the highest figures being around $55.2 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (O'Connor, 1996).

Soccer

Soccer involves physical efforts of an intermittent nature with, walking, runs, sprints

with or without the ball, jumps, sudden acceleration or deceleration (Devrnja & Matkovic, 2018). Soccer players should have very high speed, power, strength and endurance (Gabbett, Wiig & Spencer, 2013; O'Reilley, Wong, 2012). During a normal game, they run a total of about 10 km and within that endurance context, there are anaerobic explosive bursts, such as sprinting, jumping and forceful contractions. Thus, within an aerobic endurance context, there are numerous anaerobic explosive bursts of activity (Stølen et al., 2005; Abbey, Rankin, 2011; Calahorra et al., 2013). The average $VO_2\text{max}$ for elite male players is between 55 and 68 $\text{ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, with individual values of more than $70 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (Hoff, 2005). Aerobic endurance is therefore of paramount importance (Bradley, Noakes, 2013; Sarmiento et al., 2014; Varley et al., 2016). Soccer is also known to have eccentric movements such as running backwards, sudden direction changes and tackles, which lead to muscle damage (Magalhães et al., 2010; Gravina et al., 2011).

The ACE gene

The *ACE gene* is made up of 26 exons and 25 introns. Exons are coding sequences of DNA in the gene and introns are intragenic sequence/regions inside the gene. It stretches over 21 kilo bases on the chromosome 17q23. Its polymorphism consists of the presence of the (490bp *I* allele) or absence (190bp *D* allele) of a 287-base pair *Alu* repeat sequence resulting in three genotypes (*DD* and *II* homozygotes, and *ID* heterozygote) (Lin et al., 2001; Sipahi et al., 2006). The *I* allele refers to the presence of a 287 base *Alu* repeat segment in intron 16, the deletion or *D* is not likely to be the result of an actual deletion event. The presence of the intron 16 *Alu* on *ACE* expression is that of lowering activity levels of the ACE enzyme for individuals with the *I* allele.

Angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) is

part of the rennin-angiotensin-aldosterone-system (RAAS). Renin converts angiotensinogen, to angiotensin I a peptide which is in turn converted by ACE to angiotensin II vasoactive peptide. Angiotensin II is the key agent of the RAAS. It mediates vascular resistance by binding to endothelial receptors causing vasoconstriction. ACE is a key enzyme in the generation of angiotensin, a potent vasoconstrictor as well as effector of sympathetic tone, and aldosterone stimulating peptide. Angiotensin also regulates salt and water balance via the aldosterone pathway. Its action also differs among individuals due to genetic differences (Gomez-Gallego et al., 2009). Several studies have examined the effects of ACE on physical performance such as aerobic capacity, muscle function, trainability, and athletic status (Scanavini et al., 2002; Lucia et al., 2005; Amir et al., 2007).

The ACE insertion (*ACE I*) allele is prevalent in endurance athletes hence related with endurance ability (Nazarov et al., 2001). Despite research being generally inconsistent, the widely held view is that the insertion (I) allele is associated with improved performance in endurance events whereas the “deletion” (D) allele is associated with better performance in power events. However, it is not known how lower circulating ACE happens to improve performance (Wang et al., 2008). Nonetheless, it can be inferred that lower ACE in circulation could mean less conversion of angiotensin I to angiotensin II and therefore reduced vasoconstriction of blood vessels during endurance activities. The I allele is theoretically associated with a decrease in circulating levels of angiotensin II (a potent vasoconstrictor) and thus a reduction in vascular resistance which might facilitate higher cardiac output during strenuous exercise. There is an unrestricted flow of oxygen and metabolic substrates necessary for the aerobic pathways for energy production

in the skeletal muscles and other peripheral apparatus key to aerobic and ‘cardiovascular’ endurance. That would also explain the greater response to training in both the skeletal muscle and cardiovascular systems (Lucía et al., 2010). Athletes with the II genotype have greater aortic elasticity than the DD and ID genotypes (Tanriverdi et al., 2005). The I allele has also been associated with fatigue resistance in skeletal muscle (Montgomery et al., 1999). Greater percentage of the more aerobic type I skeletal muscle fibers have been found in athletes of the II genotype as compared to DD genotypes (Zhang et al., 2003). On the other hand, studies with Italian gymnasts showed the DD genotypes exhibiting higher relative strength than the II, (Calo, Vona, 2008). Similarly, a study with Caucasian Turkish female athletes showed better performance improvement in endurance with those of II genotype while those with the DD genotype improved more in the shorter more power inclined events (Cam et al., 2007). In a study of 50 to 70-year-old women the response to a 12-week varied training program showed that the ACE DD and ID did not show improvement from base line measurements in a sit to stand lower body strength test and aerobic test measured by a six-minute walk test respectively. They however showed improvements together with the II genotype group in an agility test and strength upper body arm curl test (Moraes et al., 2018). The results show some inconsistency with expected results, especially where DD would have shown association with both upper and lower strength and II not showing association with agility. In an ACE I/D variant case control study of Polish soccer players and controls, 106 players were divided into forwards, midfielders, defenders and goal keepers and there were 115 controls. Genotype and allele frequencies were not significantly different among the play positions of players neither were there

differences between the athletes and controls (Ciężczyk et al., 2016). In a similar study with 375 Brazilian soccer players of whom 90 were professionals and the other players formed strata of under 14, 15, 17 and 20 years of age, with 100 controls, the genotypic and allelic frequencies of the players in the different categories did not differ significantly from the controls (Coelho et al., 2016).

ACTN3 gene

In humans, there are two genes encoding skeletal α -actinin: ACTN2 and ACTN3 both for the structural Z discs (Bell et al., 2012). The human α -actinin-3 (ACTN3) gene encodes the structural protein α -actinin-3 in fast skeletal muscle fibers. It is located on the long arm of chromosome 11 (11q13-q14). A common polymorphism of the ACTN3 gene, 577X is due to a premature stop codon which results in a loss of function nonsense mutation. The replacement of nucleotide C (Cytosine) with T (Thymine) in exon 16 the normal codon (triplet) for Arginine (CGA) 577R is converted to the stop codon (TGA) 577X. This results in non-synthesis of the protein α -actinin-3 (North et al., 1999; MacArthur, North, 2007; Moran et al., 2007). This allele (577X) is not capable of encoding for α -actinin-3, however the presence of ACTN2 proteins in both type I and type II muscle fibers compensates for the absence of α -actinin-3 in individuals who are 577X homozygous (Calo, Vona, 2008). There are two alleles R and X, and three possible genotypes for the ACTN3 gene, which are the RR and XX homozygotes and the RX heterozygote.

The actinins (encoded by the R allele) are a group of ancient actin-binding proteins. They are limited to fast muscle fibers (type IIb) capable of generating force at high velocity (Mills et al., 2001; Vincent et al., 2007). They make up the predominant protein component

of the Z line in the type IIb muscle sarcomere to form a structure that anchors together actinin myofibrils and stabilizes the muscle contractile apparatus (Squire, 1997). They also interact with other muscle proteins in carrying out some signaling and metabolic functions (MacArthur, North, 2007). The frequency of the 577X null allele differs among different human groups. It is approximately 10% among Africans and about 18% in Caucasian populations (MacArthur et al., 2007; Norman et al., 2009). Its persistence over evolutionary time has been hypothesized to suggest that there was need to have a muscle type which would be efficient in conserving energy and resist fatigue (Calo, Vona, 2008; Head et al., 2015).

Several studies have shown substantial evidence pointing to the association of ACTN3 with physical performance. The presence of the ACTN3 protein (577R) has been shown to favor success in activities of sprint or power performance (MacArthur, North, 2005; Calo, Vona, 2008). For example, in a study of 992 Greek adolescents, male carriers of the XX genotype recorded slower sprint times compared to their RR counterparts, though this was not true for the females (Moran et al., 2007). In another study of both men and women, examining knee extensor concentric peak power, at baseline, the XX carriers showed greater strength but after a 10-week training, the RR showed greater improvement compared to both the XX and RX carriers (Delmonico et al., 2007). However, in a study of East and West African athletes, there were no significant differences between sprinters of Nigerian origin with controls and the whole group showed a very low X-allele frequency. Similar results were realized with elite Jamaican and US sprinters who classified themselves as at least 50% African American. Japanese sprinters also showed better performance by RR+RX genotypes compared to ACTN3 XX genotypes (Yang et al.,

2007; Scott et al., 2009; Mikami et al., 2014). In a study of 50 to 70-year-old women, the response to a 12-week varied training program showed that the ACTN3 XX group did not show improvement in the strength sit to stand test and the RR group did not show improvement in the 6-minute walk test (Moraes et al., 2018). This is what would be expected for XX endurance genotype and RR power genotype.

In a study of 51 untrained male Caucasians, the volume of the quadriceps was measured, knee extension, one repetition maximum and maximum power were measured through pedal sprints on an isokinetic cycle ergometer. It was established that the RR genotype was superior to the XX genotype in all the three parameters (Erskine et al., 2014). To enhance the power of association, studies which have been largely limited by small numbers, 550 best times of 346 elite Caucasian sprint athletes were collected for 100m, 200m and 400m. On average, these established that athletes with the ACTN3 577RR or the ACE DD genotype had superior best times than their ACTN3 XX and ACEII counterparts (Papadimitriou et al., 2016). However, in six studies with soccer players, a distinct relationship could not be established for sprint (anaerobic) or endurance (aerobic) performance (Santiago 2008; Pimenta et al., 2012; Pimenta et al., 2013; Eyon et al., 2014; Massidda, Scorcu & Calo, 2014; Coelho et al., 2016).

Adenosine monophosphate deaminase (AMPD1) gene

The gene AMPD1 encodes for the enzyme adenosine monophosphate 1 deaminase which catalyzes the deamination of adenosine monophosphate (AMP) to inosine monophosphate (IMP) during the formation of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) in skeletal muscle and is therefore an important muscle energy regulator during exercise (Collins, 2017; McCabe, Collins 2018). The gene is in the short arm

of chromosome one 1p13-p21 and consists of 16 exons and 15 introns. A nonsense mutation C to T in nucleotide 34 (C34T) in exon 2 (rs 17602729) of AMPD1 converts the codon CAA into the premature stop-codon TAA which results in the premature cessation of adenosine monophosphate deaminase synthesis. This gives rise to three variants of the gene CC, CT and TT, where CC genotype is normal and has no deficiency in the enzyme, and the presence of the T allele signals deficiency in the enzyme (Cieszczyk et al., 2011; Feng et al., 2017; McCabe, Collins, 2018).

In a case control study of Israelis consisting of endurance and sprinters competing at elite national level and a control group of non-athletic healthy individuals, the results of the study did not show any significant differences in the distribution of the three genotypes CC, CT and TT. However, the TT genotype frequency was very low in all the groups (Meckel et al., 2012). A study of Lithuanian athletes and controls showed a greater frequency of the CC genotypes among sprint anaerobic athletes, as compared to endurance, mixed athletes and controls. The TT genotype was absent in all the athletes and with only a 2.4% frequency in the non-athletic controls (Gineviciene et al., 2014). Similar results were obtained with student athletes engaged in high speed and strength sport versus students not doing any sport. The TT genotype was totally absent among athletes with a 3.8% frequency among non-athletes, with power lifting athletes registering a 100% CC genotype (Fedotovskaya, Danilova & Akhmetov, 2013). In another study, the mutation TT did not manifest at all in the Polish rowers but was present among the non-athletes at a percentage of 1.59% (Cieszczyk et al, 2011).

C-reactive protein (CRP)

CRP is a protein of the pentraxin family and is produced by hepatic cells and its production

is regulated by several cytokines including IL-1, IL-6, and TNF α which are secreted locally in the area of harmed tissue (Ablij, Meinders, 2002; Kitsios et al., 2013; Hayashino et al., 2014). It is made up of five identical subunits (protomers) each of which is capable of binding with two calcium units. The calcium allows CRP to bind with the phosphocholine ligands found in the cell membranes and plasma lipoproteins and as a result of this binding, phagocytosis of damaged cell materials and pathogens is facilitated (Ablij & Meinders, 2002; Michigan et al., 2011). The median concentration of CRP in serum is 0.8 mg/l. and this concentration can increase drastically following microbial infection, trauma and strenuous exercise by as much as 1000 times in a space of 48 hours (Heikkila et al., 2007; Jabs et al., 2005). These concentrations may remain high if exercise induced muscle damage remains in force (Gabay, Kushner, 1999). CRP is broken down in the liver, with a small proportion being taken care of by neutrophils and macrophages. The biological half-time of the removal of the protein from blood serum is 19 hours irrespective of the physiological or infection levels, and the significant determiner of the serum levels of CRP is the rate at which it is produced by hepatocytes. This makes it a suitable marker or indicator of the inflammation or disease activity in the body (Ablij, Meinders, 2002).

Several theories have been propounded to shade light on how exercise is likely to reduce inflammation. Loss of fat has been suggested as one of them where low levels of fat are said to reduce adipocytokines such as Interleukin 6 (IL-6) which stimulate the production of CRP from hepatocytes (Mora et al., 2006; Campbell et al., 2009). Twenty five percent of the systemic IL-6 is produced by adipocytes, and it is the IL-6 which is responsible for signaling the hepatocytes to secrete CRP. It follows then that

higher levels of body fat are likely to be associated with higher levels of CRP (Plaisance, Grandjean, 2006; Plaisance et al., 2007; Giannini et al., 2017). Some studies have shown significant weight loss together with reduction in CRP levels following physical activity or diets lowering body fat (Plaisance, Grandjean, 2006; Saghebjoos et al., 2018). Other research suggests that the increase in protein as a result of exercise also contributes to the anti-inflammatory mechanisms of exercise, probably due to antioxidant proteins from the effects of the exercise (Donges et al., 2010). Exercise generally has been shown to reduce resting levels of CRP (Mendham et al., 2011).

Aerobic based exercise programs have resulted in the reduction of CRP by various percentages. Donges et al., (2011) observed a 16.1% reduction following 10 weeks of aerobic training. Increases of up to 266% above baseline have been noted after a marathon race but returning to baseline levels by 48 hours. This has been postulated to be just a reaction to the tissue damage which is concomitant with the intense aerobic exercise. The long-term reaction is a lowered baseline level (Devrnja, Matkovic, 2018). Resistance based training programs have also been shown to reduce the levels of CRP with reductions being as much as 32% in some cases (Martins *et al.*, 2010; Donges et al., 2011). Some studies have shown that combining aerobic endurance and resistance training yields better CRP reducing results than for example the utilization of endurance training on its own (Daray et al., 2010; Ricci et al., 2018).

As earlier indicated, C-reactive protein (CRP) is a biomarker signaling subclinical inflammation and exercise induced oxidative stress in which regular physical activity of moderate intensity has been shown to reduce CRP (Mattusch et al., 2000; Fallon, Fallon & Boston, 2001). This suggests that physical activity has anti-inflammatory

properties (Powers et al., 1999).

There are however very high increases in CRP post highly competitive games in elite sports. This inflammatory response differs from sport to sport depending on the duration of the games of the sport, the metabolic load and the nature and intensity of the activities during the games. Souglis et al., 2015 compared CRP levels 13 hours post-match between soccer, basketball, handball and volleyball players. Soccer players who, on average, cover distances of 9.5 to 10.7 kilometers per game had CRP increases of 290% from base line. They were followed by basketball and handball players (120%) who, on average, cover 4 to 4.5 km per game. The lowest increase of 80% was observed among volleyball players.

Heightened levels of CRP have also been known to increase the risk of acute myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, peripheral artery disease, type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome (Hu et al., 2004).

Uric Acid

Uric acid (UA) is an endogenous antioxidant. Its levels in the body at rest are <7mg/dl in men and <6 mg/dl in women and its levels have been shown to rise in proportion to exercise intensity and training levels due to oxidative stress imposed by physical activity (Brites, 1999; Yamaner, 2010). It is recognized as one of the most significant antioxidants. It makes up the final product of purine bases (adenine and guanine) metabolism (Van Hoorenbeeck et al., 2012). Its concentration levels are related to the age, gender, body area, body weight, ethnicity and geographical position of the individual. It also constitutes 70% of the salivary antioxidant activity (Hadžović-Džuvo et al., 2011). The production of UA is stimulated by exercise and exercise increases purine oxidation. Since UA is the final product of purine

catabolism, UA concentration increases in the organism due to physical activity (Barros et al., 2012). Exercise may require the increase in the activity of adenylate cyclase acting as an additional source of energy by producing 1 ATP and 1 AMP from 2 ADP. While the ATP is used for energy, the AMP is degraded to IMP. The IMP is catabolized to hypoxanthine then xanthine, and ultimately to UA. In other words, UA is a final product of ATP degradation and increased adenine nucleotide turnover or degradation (Gailiūnienė et al., 2007; Tsalouhidou et al., 2007; Gatterer et al., 2013). This would explain why its levels rise in proportion to exercise intensity because it is a product of energy metabolism and hence an antioxidant associated with the metabolic processes of energy production during physical exercise (Svensson et al., 2002). The enzyme responsible for the conversion of xanthine to UA is xanthine oxidase and not xanthine dehydrogenase (González, et al., 2008). The antioxidant capabilities of UA are achieved by its ability to scavenge free radicals such as xanthine oxidase-free-radicals and in this way, the damage to cells by these species is minimized (Foksinski et al., 2007; Magalhães et al., 2010). UA is taken up from plasma into skeletal muscle where it reacts with reactive oxygen species in its antioxidant reactions. This is accompanied by increased formation of allantoin an oxidation product of UA in the skeletal muscles (Svensson et al., 2002). The rise in levels of UA due to exercise usually do not exceed one day and they also do not normally go above normal plasma concentration, a condition referred to as hyperuricemia (Tsalouhidou et al., 2007). Some studies have shown that chronic exercise has the effect of making the levels of UA in trained individuals higher both at rest and after exercise than in untrained non exercising individuals (Tsalouhidou et al., 2007).

Hematological acute and chronic response to exercise

Hematological parameters, just like the biochemical factors, are more sensitive indicators of responses to exercise than physical and body composition variables (Lombardi et al., 2011). Exercise stress has been known to increase leukocytes and the increase is more significant following intensive exercise. Hemoglobin and hematocrit on the other hand, will decrease, a condition known as athlete anemia and this is as a result of hemolysis and hemodilution (Kargotich et al., 2007; Suhr et al., 2009; Nazmi et al., 2014). Some studies with soccer players however have not shown a decrease in hemoglobin, hematocrit and red blood cells (Bekris et al., 2015; Santi Maria et al., 2013). This shows contradictions among various studies. In most cases, however, all the subtypes of leukocytes (neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes) increase during and after physical exertion (Kakanis et al., 2010; Morgado, et al., 2016). On the other hand, the number of eosinophils remains unchanged or decreases (Kakanis, et al., 2010).

A single bout of 2 hours of exercise at 75% of heart rate maximum caused leukocytosis in female soccer players mainly due to a significant rise of neutrophils (Avloniti et al., 2007). Similar results were obtained with male young soccer players and the increase in neutrophils was ascribed to the inflammatory nature of muscle damage (Devrnja & Matkovic, 2018). A significant decrease in percentage of hematocrit was observed immediately after a soccer game of under 21 soccer players, and only mean cell hemoglobin corpuscular increased significantly, with no change in the hemoglobin levels (Sporiš et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

Performance in sport and exercise especially at elite level is made up of a very complex interaction of the environmental or nurture

factors and the nature or genetic parameters. Research has established the association between genes and phenotype characteristics. However, it is not yet clear how the chemical and metabolic pathways function exactly to create a cause effect relationship. The exact role which genetic polymorphism plays in exercise, in individual sport and team sport still needs to be researched. This suggests that attempts by direct to consumer genetics testing by some companies to identify talent and establish what sports novice athletes may be suited for through genetic profiling is rather early and not valid. In the same vain, linking sport and exercise stress to individuals' genetic disposition also requires further research.

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